

Rationale in Commit Messages: A Survey

In this form, you will be asked a few questions about **searching for** and **assessing** rationale in commit messages.

The **rationale** in a commit message is the **reason behind** the changes introduced in the commit (the *why*).

The survey has **4 parts** and takes around **10 minutes**.

* Indique une question obligatoire

Background

Please answer a few questions regarding your background

1. 1. What developer role(s) do you have? *

Plusieurs réponses possibles.

- Open-source developer
- Open-source maintainer
- Closed-source developer (Source code not publicly available)
- Closed-source maintainer (Source code not publicly available)

2. 2. Please **name** at most three **open-source** projects that you have contributed to, separated by commas. If None, leave blank.

For example: Linux, Blender, Retrofit.

3. 3. How many years of experience do you have with **writing and/or reviewing code** ? *

Une seule réponse possible.

- 0 - 3 years
- 3 - 5 years
- 5 - 8 years
- 8 - 10 years
- 10 - 12 years
- 12 - 15 years
- more than 15 years

4. 4. How many years of experience do you have with writing and/or reviewing code **as part of your paid profession** ? *

Une seule réponse possible.

- 0 - 3 years
- 3 - 5 years
- 5 - 8 years
- 8 - 10 years
- 10 - 12 years
- 12 - 15 years
- more than 15 years

5. 5. How many years of experience do you have with **commit-based** development (e.g., using Git) ? *

Une seule réponse possible.

- 0 - 3 years
- 3 - 5 years
- 5 - 8 years
- 8 - 10 years
- 10 - 12 years
- 12 - 15 years
- more than 15 years

6. 6. On **which** task do you spend more time: **writing** commit messages or **reviewing other people's** commit messages? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	I only review commit messages	I spend more time reviewing commit messages	I spend approximately equal amount of time on both tasks	I spend more time writing commit messages	I only write commit messages
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If you contribute to **multiple** projects, please answer the following questions regarding the project **you are most active in**.

The need for **finding previous** commits in the project with **similar** decisions and/or rationale

11. 11. How **much time** do you usually **spend** searching for **previous commits** in the project with **similar** decisions and/or rationale ? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Less than 5 minutes	5-10 minutes	10-20 minutes	20-30 minutes	More than 30 minutes	Not Applicable
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>					

12. 12. How **important** it is to be able to know **all** the **previous** commits with **similar** decisions and/or rationale in the **history** of the commit messages of your software project(s) ? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Not important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. 13. Do you **use** any **tools** for finding **previous** commits in the project with **similar** decisions and/or rationale? *

Une seule réponse possible.

- Yes
 No

14. 14. If **yes**, please **list all** the tools you use below

15. 15. How **satisfied** are you with the **tools** you use? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Not Applicable
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>					

16. 16. Do you think **dedicated tool support** for finding **previous** commits with **similar** decisions and/or rationale would be **useful**? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Completely agree
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The need for **checking** for **earlier** commits in the project with **contradictory** decisions and/or rationale

17. 17. When writing or reviewing commit messages, how **often** do you check for **earlier** commits in the project with **contradictory** decisions and/or rationale? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Almost never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Almost always
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>				

21. 21. How much **time** do you usually spend looking for **earlier** commits in the project with **contradictory** decisions and/or rationale? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	less than 5 minutes	5-10 minutes	10-20 minutes	20-30 minutes	More than 30 minutes	Not Applicable
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>					

22. 22. How **important** it is to be able to identify **all earlier** commits in the history of the commit messages of your software project(s) with **contradictory** decisions and/or rationale? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Not important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

23. 23. Do you use any **tools** for finding earlier commits in the project with **contradictory** decisions and/or rationale? *

Une seule réponse possible.

- Yes
 No

24. 24. If **yes**, please **list all** the tools you use below

25. 25. How **satisfied** are you with the **tools** you use? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Not Applicable
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>					

26. 26. Do you think **dedicated tool support** for finding **earlier** commits in the project *
with **contradictory** decisions and/or rationale would be **useful** ?

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Completely agree
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The need to **assess** rationale in commit messages

27. 27. How **important** is it to the project that commit messages contain **sufficient** *
rationale?

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Not important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
For feature development:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
For future bug fixing:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
For onboarding new developers:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

29. 29. How **easy** is it to **follow** project **guidelines** when **writing** commit messages? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Not Applicable / No guidelines	Very difficult	Difficult	Neutral	Easy	Very easy
Regarding the amount of rationale:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regarding the structure of rationale:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regarding traceability (e.g., links to discussions):	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regarding consistent terminology:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

30. 30. How **often** are developers **encouraged** to add **more** rationale information in commit messages ? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Almost never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Almost always
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>				

31. 31. How **important** is it to **maintain consistent** rationale **practices** across **time** *
in your software project(s) ?

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Not important	Somewhat important	Very important	Extremely important
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

32. 32. How **often** are developers **encouraged** to **rephrase** commit messages for **consistency** with the rest of the project ? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Almost never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Almost always
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>				

33. 33. Do you **use** any tools for **assessing** rationale in commit messages? *

Une seule réponse possible.

- Yes
 No

34. 34. If **yes**, please list **all** the tools you use

35. 35. How **satisfied** are you with these tools? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Not Applicable
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>					

36. 36. Do you think **dedicated tool support** for **assessing rationale** in commit messages would be **useful**? *

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Completely disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Completely agree
Answer:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thank you for taking the survey!

37. We develop **tools** to help **developers** better **understand rationale** in commit histories.

If you consent to be asked for **an optional follow-up interview**, please add **your email address** below.

38. If you have **any other feedback**, feel free to let us know below.

Ce contenu n'est ni rédigé, ni cautionné par Google.

Google Forms